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An overview of
DIVE SHOW
attendance
a supply and demand perspective

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This research forms part of the Green Bubbles RISE Project

Green Bubbles

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1. INTRODUCTION

Exhibitions and fairs play a significant role in event tourism. Unfortunately, limited to no research exists regarding dive shows – both from a supply or demand side and the role that these shows play in the sustainability of the diving industry. For exhibitors, dive shows create a platform for networking as well as to increase brand visibility in the minds of potential new and existing clients. For visitors (divers), attending dive shows creates opportunities for personal face-to-face contact with suppliers, to socialise and be exposed to the latest trends in the diving industry. Nevertheless, there is currently no empirical data available on specifically the needs from both a supply and demand side perspective. To fill the gap in the current research regarding dive shows, this research had the following three key areas of interest:

- Dive shows and related expos provide necessary exposure to the diving industry, services, and products – but attendance is expensive. Do operators and exhibitors really benefit?
- Technological advances and globalisation influence the consumer – do divers/visitors still have the need to attend dive shows in person?
- How 'green' is the diving industry (suppliers and consumers) – Are there a place and a need for more environmentally friendly initiatives at dive shows?

To provide answers to the questions above, the research was conducted over a period of three years to gain an overview of the role of dive shows, both from a supply and demand perspective. The research started in 2014 and was completed in March 2017. This research forms part of the Green Bubbles Rise Project. The Green Bubbles project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 643712. Please note that this report reflects only the researchers' views. The Research Executive Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

2. METHOD OF RESEARCH

The research was conducted in three phases: 1) Operators' opinions regarding dive shows in the two case studies (Portofino, Italy and Ponta do Ouro, Mozambique); 2) exhibitors' opinions; and 3) divers' opinions regarding dive show attendance. Semi-structured interviews were held in all cases and the methodology followed in each phase is outlined in each separate section. However, in all cases, descriptive statistics were used to profile the respondents. The interviews were transcribed into text and presented in a narrative form. In the cases where the interviews were in Italian, the recordings were first translated and then transcribed. Creswell's six steps in data analysis and interpretation were used to analyse the data. These included: Step 1: Organise and prepare the data; Step 2: Read through all the data; Step 3: Begin a detailed analysis of a coding process; Step 4: Use the coding process to generate a description of the setting or people as well as categories or themes for analysis; Step 5: Propose the description and themes represented in the qualitative narrative; and Step 6: Make an interpretation of or explain the meaning of the data (Creswell, 2009). Trustworthiness for this study was accomplished by means of peer examination, coding, and recoding the data. Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethics Committee of the North-West

University (Potchefstroom Campus: EMS2016/11/04-0210, EMS2016/11/04-0211, EMS2016/11/04-0212). Consent was furthermore obtained from all participants before the interviews were conducted. The different parties were requested to grant permission to ensure informed and voluntary participation. All the participants were also advised that their identity would be protected and that they could withdraw from the research project at any time.

In the sections to follow, the findings from the research will be discussed.

3. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

3.1 DIVE SHOW ATTENDANCE BY PORTOFINO OPERATORS 2015

3.1.1 Introduction and method of research

During the first phase of the research, dive operators in the case study in Italy, Portofino, were interviewed. Six operators formed part of the research and the interviews were conducted during September and October 2015. The majority of interviews were conducted in Italian and translated to English before being transcribed. The main objectives of the interviews were to determine the following:

1. The socio-demographic and business profile of operators in Portofino.
2. The level of productivity of the dive centre/charter.
3. The operators' opinions regarding dive shows.

The results are consequently discussed.

3.1.2 Demographic profile of dive operators interviewed in Portofino 2015

On average, the participants were 45 years old, the majority were from Italy (five of the six operators interviewed, while Participant 5 was from Peru), not married (Participants 1 and 4) or divorced (Participant 3 and 5), while Participant 2 was married and Participant 6 was in a relationship. Participants 1, 2, 4, 5 and 6 were all male, while only one participant was female (17%) (Participant 3). A diploma was the highest level of education, while Participant 1 had a professional qualification and Participant 2 a PhD in Biological Sciences. Regarding their experience as divers, on average, the participants have been diving for 18 years, log on average 122 dives per year, and have logged over 2 710 dives thus far. Due to their longer years actively diving (over 20 years), Participant 2 followed by Participant 1 have logged the most dives while Participant 4 logs the most dives per year. The four participants indicated that they have a variety of diving certifications ranging from Advanced, Rescue, Open Water, Instructor, and Dive Master. The majority of their diving certifications were obtained through PADI (see Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic profile of operators interviewed

Participant	Gender	Age	Place of origin	Level of education	Marital status	Number of years diving	Estimated number of dives logged	Average number of dives logged per year	Diving certifications	Diving agency/company where certifications were obtained
Participant 1	Male	50	Italy	Professional Degree in Biological Sciences	Not married	20	3500	150	Advanced Dive Master Instructor Instructor emergency first response Instructor IDC staff Instructor MSDT Instructor naturalist Instructor nitrox Instructor peak performance buoyancy Instructor Reef Check Instructor wreck Instructor open water diver Research and Recovery Instructor	PADI Reef Check
Participant 2	Male	48	Italy	PhD in Biological Sciences	Married	23	5000	100	Open water diver Advanced Rescue Divemaster Instructor (Master, Emergency first response, nitrox, wreck, digital underwater photography, and navigation) IDC staff Deepwater Deep air	PADI NASDS TSA
Participant 3	Female	46	Italy	Diploma	Divorced	15	3000	Did not indicate	Deepwater Digital underwater photography Instructor Nitrox Research and recovery Side Mount Tech Diver Tec Trimix Wreck	PADI PADI+SSI TDI UTD DSAT
Participant 4	Male	32	Italy	Diploma	Not married	14	800	200	Base Advanced Deep Wreck Nitrox Rescue Dive Master Instructor	FIAS PADI TDI
Participant 5	Male	40	Peru	Diploma	Divorced	19	2000	100	Advanced Dive Master Emergency first response Instructor (Emergency first response, gas blender, tech deep, Tech Trimix, Master) Open water Rescue	PADI
Participant 6	Male	59	Italy	Diploma	In a relationship	18	2000	60	Advanced Deep Digital underwater photography Divemaster Emergency first response Open water Instructor Rescue Wreck Tech 50	PADI

3.1.3 Business profile of dive centres/charters

In terms of the business profile of the centre/charters (see Table 2), 75% of the dive centres were located in Santa Margherita (Participant 1, 2 and 4), while Participant 3 was based in San Miguel, Participant 5 in Rapallo and Participant 6 in Genova. On average, the dive centres/charters were 11 years old, while the participants have been involved with their respective charter for eight years. However, on average, participants have 14 years' experience either working or owning a dive centre or charter. Participants 1 and 2 had the most years' experience, respectively 19 and 18 years, followed by Participants 5 and 6 who both had 16 years' experience. It is evident that the participants have multiple roles and responsibilities in their respective dive centre/charter. Five of the six participants indicated that they were the owners, while Participants 1, 2 and 3 also indicated that they were the manager, an instructor as well as a dive guide. Participant 6 indicated that he was the manager. Participant 2 also acts as the CEO, while Participant 1 also acts as an environmental educator. On average, the participants employ six staff members and own one to two boats. Regarding additional services offered by the dive centres/charters, Participants 1, 2 and 6 also offer repairs, while Participant 1 also indicated offering to volunteer, Participant 2 offers research-related activities, Participant 3 computes security, Participant 4 indicated to offer no additional services, and Participant 5 offers a leisure course.

3.1.4 Level of productivity

In terms of productivity (Table 3), the participating dive centres/charters have registered an average of 6 000 dives in 2010, 4 667 in 2011, 3 250 in 2012, 2 840 in 2013 and 3 140 in 2014. A gradual decline in the number of dives registered could be observed over the five years, with a slight increase in 2014. Regarding the number of courses registered, again a gradual decline could be observed. On average, 160 courses were registered in 2010, 158 in 2011, 151 in 2012, 116 in 2013, and 108 in 2014. Participant 1 and Participant 4's dive centre/charter registered the most dives since 2010, while Participant 6 registered the most courses. From Table 3, it is clear that June to September is high season for all the participating dive centres/charters, while Participants 1 and 4 also indicated that their diving season starts in May and Participant 5's dive season starts in April. Participant 1 also indicated that October still experiences a high number of divers.

Table 2: Business profile of operators interviewed in Portofino

Participant	Location of dive centre	Age of dive centre (number of years operating)	Number of years working for/at dive centre	Number of years' experience in dive charters	Role in dive centre	Activities offered by dive centre	Number of staff employed	Number of boats owned by dive centre
Participant 1	Santa Margherita Liguria	20	12	19	Owner Manager Instructor Dive guide Environmental educator	Repairs Volunteering	6	2
Participant 2	Santa Margherita Liguria	0	0	18	Owner CEO Manager Instructor Dive guide	Repairs Research	5	2
Participant 3	San Miguel	5	5	10	Owner Instructor Dive guide	Computing security	4	1
Participant 4	Santa Margherita Liguria	4	4	3	Owner	No other activities	4	2
Participant 5	Rapallo	10	10	16	Owner Instructor	Leisure courses	3	3
Participant 6	Genova	25	18	16	Manager	Repairs Shop	15	3

Table 3: Level of productivity of operators interviewed in Portofino

Participant	Number of dives (d) and courses (c)					Level of productivity during year											
	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
Participant 1	(d) 8000	(d) 7000	(d) 7000	(d) 6000	(d) 6000	None	Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very high	Very high	Very high	Very high	High	Low	None
	(c) 100	(c) 100	(c) 80	(c) 70	(c) 70												
Participant 2						Low	None	Low	Moderate	Moderate	High	Very high	Very high	High	Moderate	Low	Low
Participant 3				(d) 1200	(d) 1700	Low	None	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Very high	Very high	High	Very high	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
				(c) 15	(c) 20												
Participant 4	(d) 8000	(d) 5000	(d) 3000	(d) 3000	(d) 3000	Low	None	Low	Moderate	High	Very high	Very high	Very high	Very high		Moderate	Low
					(c) 50												
Participant 5	(d) 2000	(d) 2000	(d) 2000	(d) 3000	(d) 4000	None	Fair	Moderate	High	High	Very high	High	High	Fair	None	None	
	(c) 30	(c) 23	(c) 23	(c) 30	(c) 40												
Participant 6			(d) 1000	(d) 1000	(d) 1000	Fair	Fair	Fair	Moderate	Moderate	High	High	High	High	Moderate	Fair	Fair
	(c) 350	(c) 350	(c) 350	(c) 350	(c) 300												

3.1.5 Attendance of Dive Shows

According to Table 4, apart from Participant 2, all five other participants indicated that they have attended dive shows in the past three years. These shows were mainly Eudi held in Bologna, or Boot held in Düsseldorf. Participant 5 also attended the Dema show in the United States, while Participant 6 appears to have the most diverse dive show attendance. Participants indicated that the main reasons for attending or exhibiting at dive shows are to promote their business, to grow their client base and to network with the industry. When selecting dive shows to attend, the ability of the dive show to create access to major source markets is essential, followed by convenience. Unfortunately, many participants indicated their reluctance to continue their attendance to dive shows in the future. This is mainly due to the content of the shows changing due to the withdrawal of major production houses over the years, which negatively influenced visitor numbers. Many participants also feel that attendance is expensive, not value-for-money and return-on-investment is low, which is a concern for the future sustainability of dive shows. The majority of participants stated no need for more dive shows internationally; however, more localised fairs and shows should be held in the MPA (Marine Protected Area). Regarding more environmentally friendly campaigns at dive shows, the participants expressed mixed feelings. While the majority indicated the importance of such campaigns and initiatives, they feel that dive shows may not be the ideal platform for this, since visitors are already overwhelmed at dive shows. The participants expressed that it is the individual diver and dive operators' responsibility to implement this behaviour.

3.1.6 Recommendations made by participants

The operators in Portofino made the following recommendations:

- Dive shows are currently too expensive. More affordable packages for dive operators who want to exhibit are required.
- Dive operators/charters in Portofino should not exhibit separate from the MPA. Rather, the Portofino MPA should have a stand that promotes all the diving activities and centres as this would be more cost effective.
- Greater collaboration is required between the different dive operators in Portofino and the MPA. Ideally, the MPA should attend dive shows and promote the area and all operators as a unity.

Table 4: Attendance of dive shows

Participant	Dive show attendance in the past 3 years	Dive Shows attended in past 3 years	Reasons for attending dive shows	On average, how many dive shows per year	Reasons for not attending	Average budget for attending dive shows	Dive shows regarded as value-for-money.	Envisaged outcomes from attending	Key aspects when selecting dive shows to attend/exhibit at	Need for more dive shows locally and internationally	Importance of environmentally friendly initiatives at dive shows
Participant 1	Yes	Eudi in Bologna Boot in Düsseldorf	Promotion of business Build client base Exposure of business to potential new clients	Do not attend any more	Over the years, one tends to reach a saturation point, especially at Italian shows. Return on investment becomes low. Attendance now more relevant to producers of diving products/ services.	Depends on the Dive Show and length of the Show. Budgets approximately €7000.	Not value for money as a return on investment is low from attending. However, return-on-investment is not immediately and bookings sometimes only evident years after attending.	To build a solid client base.	Dive show should be a place where key diving markets can be reached.	No, already too many.	Is of the opinion that people who attend dive shows are not interested in such campaigns. These initiatives should be in collaboration with certifying agencies and projects and be presented locally.
Participant 2	No	N/A	N/A	Do not attend any more	Too expensive to attend /exhibit.	N/A	Not value-for-money considering the costs – too expensive.	To build and retain a solid client base. Promotion of business and offered packages.	Convenience and location.	No, already too many.	No need for these initiatives at dive shows – believes that the market will not be interested.
Participant 3	Yes	Eudi in Bologna	Exposure of business to clients.	N/A	Exhibited for years but do not event attend as only visitors now since attendance is not value-for-money and return on investment is low. Feels that dive shows are more beneficial to producers, certifying agencies and schools but not for charters wanting to increase their client base.	N/A	No, too expensive and return on investment is low. However considering attending Boot in the future to possibly reach a different market.	N/A	N/A	More local dive shows needed in the area especially one held in the MPA and sponsored by the MPA.	Feels it is an important aspect; however, not necessarily at dive shows. Feels that it is every operator and individual's own responsibility.
Participant 4	Yes	Eudi in Bologna	To promote business.	One event per year	N/A	Approximately €1 300 (can share stand costs)	Yes since costs can be shared.	Promotion of business To reach potential clients To network with other operators and suppliers.	N/A	No, since it is already expensive to attend, does not feel the need for attending more shows during a year.	Yes, divers should be taught about the proper conduct under water and on the proper diving practices. However, using the term 'sustainability' should be rethought since many people misinterpret the term. People also want to see tangible outcomes and progress of the concept.

Participant 5	Yes	Eudi in Bologna Boot in Düsseldorf Dema, United States	Exposure of business to clients. Exposure to latest trends and products in the Industry. Eudi: because it is one the biggest dive show in Italy. Boot: to diversify their client base and to increase the number of foreign divers. Dema: exposure to latest trends, equipment and packages before they are launched in Italy.	Two events per year	No return on investment.	Various expenses but could share expenses due to partnership. Approximately €4 000-€5 000.	No, no return on investment or new clients because of attending. Attending dive shows is a long-term investment but due to recession, it is much more difficult to attend. Boot is too long and time-consuming (10 days), therefore very expensive and the language barrier makes it difficult to liaise with the organisers and potential clients as they prefer to speak in German.	Mainly for exposure and to attract new clients. Personal contact and interaction with potential new and existing clients.	Must create opportunities to reach main and new target markets.	Already too many dive shows in Europe. However attending and organising more will depend on your main objectives and which target markets you want to reach.	There should be more green initiatives, however feels that people are not interested in it at dive shows.
Participant 6	Yes	Genova Dive show (helps to organise the event with local authorities, production homes and diving centres) Salon de la Plongée (Paris Dive Show) Eudi in Bologna Boot in Dusseldorf	To attract clients and sell products. To promote online store.	Several events a year.	Eudi's popularity is declining since quality has decreased and main production homes no longer exhibit there.	N/A	Yes especially to remain visible to clients.	Increase client base and to sell products.	N/A	N/A	N/A

3.2 DIVE SHOW ATTENDANCE BY PONTA DO OURO OPERATORS

2015/2016

3.2.1 Introduction and method of research

For the second part of phase 1, dive operators in the second case study in Ponta do Ouro, Mozambique were interviewed. Five operators formed part of the research and the interviews were conducted during November 2015 and February 2016. The main objectives of the interviews were similar to those for the operators in Portofino and were as follows:

1. The socio-demographic and business profile of operators in Ponta do Ouro.
2. The level of productivity of the dive centre/charter.
3. The operators' opinions regarding dive shows.

The results are consequently discussed.

3.2.2 Demographic and business profile of dive operators interviewed in Portofino 2015/16

Unfortunately, the interviewed participants did not provide complete demographic and business profile information. Tables 5 to 7 indicate the provided information. The majority of participants were female (80%) while only Participant 5 was male. All the operators interviewed are located in Ponta do Ouro. The average age of the participants was 37 years. Participants 2-4 indicated that they originated from South Africa while Participants 1 and 5 did not indicate their origin. The participants indicated that they were instructors or had open water diving certifications. On average, the businesses were 11 years old while the participants indicated that they had been involved with their particular dive charter an average of 9 years and had an average of 10 years' experience. Participant 3's business was the oldest compared to the other participants interviewed. Three of the five participants interviewed were the owners of the business while Participants 2 and 4 were also the managers. Regarding additional services or activities offered by the businesses, it is clear from Table 6 that the participants offer a variety of services and activities along with diving. On average, the businesses have nine staff members and one boat. In terms of the level of productivity (Table 7), it is difficult to make assumptions due the lack of information obtained. However, it can be observed that high season is November to January, March and April, July and September. The high levels of productivity during these months could be explained by the fact that the South African school holidays are usually in these months.

Table 5: Demographic profile of operators interviewed

Participant	Gender	Age	Place of origin	Level of education	Marital status	Number of years diving	Estimated number of dives logged	Average number of dives logged per year	Diving certifications	Diving agency/company where certifications were obtained
Participant 1	Female	Did not indicate	Did not indicate	Did not indicate	Did not indicate	Did not indicate	Did not indicate	Did not indicate	Did not indicate	Did not indicate
Participant 2	Female	26	South Africa	Matric	Not married	2	Did not indicate	Did not indicate	Open water	
Participant 3	Female	45	South Africa	Diploma	Married	21	100	Did not indicate	Open water Advanced	NAUI
Participant 4	Female	40	South Africa	Degree	Single	Did not indicate	Did not indicate	Did not indicate	Instructor	PADI
Participant 5	Male	Did not indicate	Did not indicate	Did not indicate	Did not indicate	Did not indicate	Did not indicate	Did not indicate	Instructor	

Table 6: Business profile of operators interviewed in Ponta do Ouro

Participant	Location of dive centre	Age of dive centre (number of years operating)	Number of years working for/at dive centre	Number of years' experience in dive charters	Role in dive centre	Activities offered by dive centre	Number of staff employed	Number of boats owned by dive centre
Participant 1	Ponta do Ouro, Mozambique	Did not indicate	Did not indicate	Did not indicate	Did not indicate	Did not indicate	Did not indicate	Did not indicate
Participant 2	Ponta do Ouro, Mozambique	8	2	2	Manager	No activities Marine mammal ecotourism	17	
Participant 3	Ponta do Ouro, Mozambique	18	18	18	Owner CEO Dive guide	Research Volunteering Marine mammal ecotourism	5	Did not indicate
Participant 4	Ponta do Ouro, Mozambique	7	7		Owner Manager Dive Master	Courses: PADI Specialities PADI & Sharklife Airfills: Air plus Nitrox Equipment hire Night Dives	5	1
Participant 5	Ponta do Ouro, Mozambique	Did not indicate	Did not indicate	Did not indicate	Owner	Casual Diving Discover Scuba Diving Courses Open Water Scuba Diving Course to Dive Master Course Ocean Safaris Sunset Cruises Snorkelling trips Shark diving Photography Videography	Did not indicate	1

Table 7: Level of productivity of operators interviewed in Portofino

Participant	Number of dives (d) and courses (c)					Level of productivity during year											
	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
Participant 1	Did not indicate					Did not indicate											
	Did not indicate					Did not indicate											
Participant 2	Did not indicate					High	Moderate	High	High	Fair	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	High	Very high
Participant 3	Did not indicate					High	Fair	Fair	Very high	Fair	Fair	High	Moderate	High	Moderate	Fair	Very high
Participant 4	Did not indicate					Did not indicate											
Participant 5	Did not indicate					Did not indicate											

3.2.3 Attendance of dive shows

It can be observed from Table 8 that all but one operator (Participant 2) has attended dive shows in the past three years. Since only one major show is held in South Africa, the Getaway Show in Johannesburg, which combines outdoor activities, boating, and diving, the majority of participants indicated they attended this show. Participant 3 attended smaller regional fairs and seminars, while Participant 5 employs travel agents to market the business internationally. It is, however, clear that the participants were attending dive shows less frequently; however, this could be due to the limited number of shows held in South Africa. The main reasons for attending dive shows were to increase brand visibility, to network, and to reach new and existing clients (increase sales). When choosing dive shows to attend, Participant 1 indicated that the reputation and standing of the show play a major role in their decision. Participants, however, indicated that attending dive shows is expensive and return-on-investments are low; therefore, many feel attending is not value-for-money. Regarding the need for more dive shows, the participants had mixed feelings. Participants 1, 2 and 3 expressed the need for more shows, especially smaller, local events in Mozambique, while Participants 4 and 5 were of the opinion that there are enough smaller shows during the year and there is no need for more than one big show such as the Getaway Show. All five participants indicated that more green initiatives and campaigns would be welcome at these shows, especially since consumers are becoming increasingly conscious of such campaigns.

3.2.4 Recommendations made by participants

The participants, regarding the general management of dive shows, made the following recommendations and suggestions:

- Communication from organisers should improve, especially in terms of awareness of when these shows are taking place.
- There should be more interactive displays to expose people to diving.
- More expos available in areas such as Ponta do Ouro, especially since travelling to South Africa is expensive.
- Improve the overall planning and marketing of dive shows. The participants mentioned instances where colleagues set up events for a particular year; however, the dates were not fixed; four to six months' notice would be good to allow better planning.
- Shows should be more affordable.

Table 8: Attendance of Dive Shows

Participant	Dive show attendance in the past 3 years	Dive shows attended in past 3 years	Reasons for attending dive shows	On average, how many dive shows per year	Reasons for not attending	Average budget for attending dive shows	Dive Shows regarded as value-for-money?	Envisaged outcomes from attending	Key aspects when selecting dive shows to attend/exhibit at	Need for more dive shows in South Africa?	Importance of environmentally friendly initiatives at dive shows
Participant 1	Yes	Three smaller dive shows Getaway Show in Johannesburg	To continue with brand visibility. An opportunity to reach a niche market. To build contacts. Face-to-face interaction with potential new and existing clients.	Use to be 1 a year.	Stopped attending shows 2-3 years ago since the return on investment was too low. Getaway show used to be combined with a boat and diving show and this attracted many potential divers; however, the boat show was excluded later and this negatively influenced the number of specifically divers to the show. The diving part at shows usually very small and among outdoor activities so visibility and exposure of dive stands are low.	Various expenses, approximately R15 000-R20 000.	Yes, if one can reach clients and generate bookings. However, return-on-investments are usually over the long-term so patience is key.	Increased brand visibility.	The reputation of the Show – well-known brand. Potential of the show to attract a large number of visitors.	Yes, and these shows should be combined with boat shows to attract a broader market. However, hosting these types of events across the country is difficult as one does not necessarily want to attract divers from all over – diving is expensive so it would not be cost-effective to market in regions where people cannot afford to dive.	Yes, used to try to incorporate aspects regarding the sustainability of the ocean in their stands. More initiatives are required at shows since people are becoming more conscious.
Participant 2	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	Stopped attending since it was not worth attending in terms of expenses.	N/A	Too expensive to attend considering especially travelling costs from Ponta do Ouro.	N/A	N/A	Yes. If they did host a small seminar with valuable information it would help the community. Would consider attending the DAN expo.	Yes, because people become more aware of what needs to be the right conduct underwater.
Participant 3	Yes	Presentations at museums and conferences.	N/A	1-2 a year.	N/A	Approximately R12 000.	Attending is expensive and it takes a long time before you see the benefit of being there.	Networking and education on certain species that they work with.	N/A	Definitely locally. There are many conferences but money and time are problems that make attendance difficult.	Definitely yes.
Participant 4	Yes	Getaway Show in Johannesburg.	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Reaching new clients.	N/A	There are so many already in SA; however, unsure about any in Mozambique.	Yes and look for those.

Participant 5	Yes	Various shows, especially internationally.	N/A	Various shows throughout the year, however, agents overseas promote the business on their behalf.	N/A	N/A	N/A	To sell diving holiday, packages, they only sell the package and not diving alone.	N/A	Locally we have one in Johannesburg; SA does not really need more than one. Dive shows are important definitely because people go there to book dive holidays and see where they prefer to go. It is a travel agency.	Yes, the way the world is going with everything must be green, people are very aware these days of environmental issues. People like to see that kind of thing.
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3.3 EXHIBITORS AT BOOT 2016

3.3.1 Introduction and method of research

The second phase of the research focused on exhibitors' opinion regarding dive shows. Ten interviews were conducted during Boot 2016. The main objective of this phase was to determine exhibitors' opinion regarding the relevance and value of attending and exhibiting at dive shows.

3.3.2 Exhibitors' opinions regarding Dive Shows

Regarding the profile of the participants (Table 9), 70% of the interviewees were male and 30% were female. The majority of participants were from Germany (70%), while Participant 1 was from South Africa, Participant 7 from Italy and Participant 8 from Egypt. A variety of diving-related companies were included in the interviews, ranging from diving equipment, medical aids and insurance, diving destinations, and diving magazines. On average, participants and their respective business have exhibited at Boot for 14 years. With regard to the main reasons why the participants' companies exhibit at Boot, the following recurring themes were observed: to sustain current client base, face-to-face interaction with clients, to network, exposure of company/destination/brand and to increase sales. Many participants also noted that Boot is the largest and most important dive show in Europe and is, therefore, the ideal place to connect with main target markets. Many (80%) also attend other smaller, regional or national events. All participants indicated that exhibiting at Boot is very expensive and although their presence cannot always be regarded as value-for-money in terms of expenses, the loss would be greater if they did not attend. Over the long term, exhibiting is worth the costs. All the participants further indicated that dive shows are relevant to the diving industry and without them personal, face-to-face interaction with clients and suppliers would not be possible. Many participants also noticed a change in the needs of the market especially due to the influence of technology and the internet. This has forced them to adapt especially their marketing to meet the needs of the visitors. While printed traditional marketing material is no longer that relevant, they still combine both printed and electronic promotional material. Participants expressed divided opinions regarding more environmental awareness campaigns at dive shows. Many participants were of the opinion that the market shows no need for it as visitors are already overwhelmed at the shows. They do, however, feel that such initiatives are the individual dive operations and businesses' own responsibility. Participant 7 noted that exposure to the diving industry and educational programmes and campaigns are necessary, especially since many school groups attend the show. Exposure to these initiatives should, therefore, be from a young age.

Table 9: Exhibitors' opinions regarding dive shows

Participant	Gender	Origin	Type of business	Number of previous attendances	Reasons for exhibiting at Boot	Number of dive shows per year	Average costs to attend and exhibit	Attendance value-for-money?	Relevance of dive shows to diving industry	Need for more environmentally friendly initiatives at show	Observed changes in the market attending Boot
Participant 1	Male	South Africa	Diving expeditions and marine logistics	11	Remaining relevant to clients = establishing a loyal customer base. Boot is the biggest and most important Dive Show in Europe. To ensure business over the long-term.	Only, Boot, Dusseldorf Germany	R200 000	Over short-term no, however, return on investments over the long-term.	N/A	No, nobody will be interested.	N/A
Participant 2	Female	Germany	Medical assistance and insurance	14	To gain access to the main market. To network with co-operation partners. To sell and give exposure to products. To establishing and retaining relationships (clients and partners)	Eudi in Bologna, Italy Dive Travel Show in Madrid, Spain European Congress of Biomedical Society (EUBS) Local fairs, symposiums, and events organised by company	N/A various expenses	Exhibiting is very expensive, however, it is necessary to remain relevant and visible in the minds of customers.	Very relevant especially for personal contact with customers.	Important, however, it should be marketed more.	Change in the market can be observed – technology plays a role. Influences the way business is marketed – need a combination of printed and electronic marketing material.
Participant 3	Male	Germany	Underwater equipment	3	To show and inform the public of products. Meeting with partners. General networking	Dema Show, United States	N/A various expenses	Yes, exhibiting is value for money even though it is very expensive.	N/A	Yes, however, it should be every diver and individual companies' responsibility.	N/A
Participant 4	Female	Germany	Diving magazine	7	Networking with clients and the industry. To acquire new clients – build readership. To liaise with other exhibitors for advertisements.	InterDive trade show for diving, snorkelling and traveling in Germany Smaller, local fairs, symposiums, and events	N/A various expenses	Yes, especially for personal contact with clients as well as to build and establish new relationships with potential clients and the industry.	Extremely relevant for the personal relationships with clients and the industry – Dive Shows provide a platform for personal interaction to take place.	N/A	Change in the market can be observed – technology plays a role. Influences the way business is marketed – need a combination of printed and electronic marketing material. Recently updated website to attract more readers, however, printed material is still relevant especially since they are a magazine.

Participant 5	Female	Germany	Scuba diving tours and destination resort	15	<p>Boot is the biggest and most important Dive Show in Europe.</p> <p>To gain access to the main target market (Europe).</p> <p>For face-to-face communication with clients.</p> <p>Building new clients.</p> <p>To support agents.</p> <p>To give past clients the chance to see new products on offer.</p>	Various international dive shows in Australia, United States, and Asia.	N/A various expenses	Value-for-money due to the personalised interaction with clients.	Extremely relevant to have personalised face-to-face interaction with existing and new clients.	Yes, while the resorts they promote implement suitable practices, it is not marketed at the Dive Show. Should perhaps be something to consider in the future.	Although the markets' needs have changed in terms of marketing, they still rely on printed media i.e. flyers in conjunction with electronic and virtual promotional material.
Participant 6	Male	Germany	High-pressure compressor manufacturer	15	<p>To reach the main target market.</p> <p>To increase sales of products.</p>	Eudi in Bologna, Italy. Various international Dive Shows.	Various expenses.	Yes especially in terms of meeting new clients and building a relationship with existing clients.	Extremely relevant to have personalised face-to-face interaction with existing and new clients.	Yes, however very limited at Dive Shows.	Markets' needs have changed, however; personal, face to face interaction and communication will always be relevant.
Participant 7	Male	Italy	Scuba diving equipment	20	<p>Boot is the biggest and most important Dive Show in Europe.</p> <p>To reach the main target market.</p> <p>Exposure of business and products.</p> <p>To increase sales of products.</p> <p>To hear critiques from final customers.</p> <p>Networking with the industry and other manufacturers.</p>	Dive Shows in the United States and France. Regional fairs in The Netherlands and Great Britain.	Various expenses, approximately €70 000.	Yes, attending Dive Shows is an investment.	Extremely relevant as it serves as a platform to connect with clients and other manufacturers.	Yes, however very limited at dive shows. However, it should be expanded especially since many school groups attend the dive shows. Children should be exposed from an early age.	Technology plays a significant role in the markets' changing needs especially the internet. Online sales have increased and many fear that shops will become irrelevant as people can order everything online. However, people will always need personal communication and interaction since scuba diving is a hobby and a sport that is being sold.
Participant 8	Male	Egypt	Diving destination	10	<p>Boot is the biggest and most important dive show in Europe.</p> <p>To increase the visibility of destination.</p> <p>To attract new customers.</p> <p>To retain existing customers.</p> <p>Networking with travel agents and suppliers to find new products.</p>	No, since Europeans are the main target market for the destination and Boot, therefore, is ideal to reach the market.	Various expenses.	Yes, although expensive to attend and exhibit at, attending is a long-term investment.	Yes definitely. Even though people can read about the destination on the internet, one gets a different experience when talking to people from that destination in person. Personal face-to-face interaction will always be important.	Very important, however very limited at dive shows.	No longer had a use for printed promotional material since visitors are no longer interested in e.g. brochures.

Participant 9	Male	Germany	Diving insurance	25	<p>Boot is the biggest and most important dive show in Europe.</p> <p>Central meeting place from worldwide diving (all organisations, training organisations and dive clubs are present).</p> <p>To create an opportunity for members to renew their membership.</p> <p>To sell products and material.</p> <p>To increase memberships.</p> <p>To answer questions from clients (experts can talk to clients).</p> <p>To establish and reinforce a strong brand identity.</p>	Various smaller dive shows and seminars in Europe.	Various expenses, approximately €50 000	Not value for money, however, the cost will be more to not exhibit at the show.	N/A	An important aspect, however, the market and reasons why they attend dive shows are not interested in such messages – people are already overwhelmed.	N/A
Participant 10	Male	Germany	Diving magazine	21	<p>Boot is the biggest and most important dive show in Europe.</p> <p>To increase readership.</p> <p>To build new contacts for advertising.</p>	Dema Show, United States InterDive trade show for diving, snorkelling and traveling in Germany	Various expenses.	Yes, value for money, especially since readership, greatly increases after attending.	Yes, especially to increase readerships.	Yes, however, they use the magazine as a platform to educate divers. Do not feel it will be relevant at dive shows – can reach more people through the magazine.	N/A

3.4 DIVERS TO THE EUROPEAN DIVE SHOW (EUDI) 2016

3.4.1 Introduction and method of research

Divers attending dive shows were the target group for the third phase of the research. Since EUDI is one of the most popular dive shows in Italy and the show that the majority of operators in Portofino attend, 31 interviews were conducted during the show in 2016. The interviews were all in Italian and translated to English before being transcribed. The purpose of the research was the following:

- To determine the demographic profile of divers to the show.
- To determine their attendance and reasons for attending the show.
- To determine to what extent they regard environmentally campaigns at the show as important.

The findings are consequently discussed.

3.4.2 Demographic profile of participants interviewed

As shown in Table 10, the majority of the participants were male (71%), while 29% were female. The average age of participants were 40 years and they originated from either Italy (94%) or Sardinia (6%). The majority of respondents either were from Bologna or from Cuneo (16% each), followed by participants travelling from Milan (13%), Faenza, Ferrara and Torino (10% respectively). The participants indicated a variety of occupations. On average, the participants have been diving for 11 years with instructor (19%) and advanced (13%) revealed as the most prevalent diving certifications. Participants indicated that they prefer to dive in the Liguria, the lakes in Italy, Sicily, the islands of Sardinia, the Maldives, and the Red Sea.

3.4.3 Dive Show attendance

Regarding their attendance to Eudi, participants attended Eudi for only one day, travelled in groups of two persons, and had an average budget to attend the show of €398.67. The main reasons for attending the show included the passion for diving, out of curiosity, to meet new people, to catch up with other people, to buy new equipment such as wetsuits and to gain valuable exposure to the latest diving equipment and trends. The majority of the participants (58%) indicated they were only planning to attend Eudi during 2016, followed by 19% who indicated that they were also planning to attend the Genova Dive Show, while 9% indicated that they also attended Boot.

3.4.4 Opinions regarding environmentally friendly initiatives at dive shows

Only 13% of the participants were aware of any green initiatives at Eudi. These participants were aware of only Reef Check. The remaining 87% of the participants presented mixed feelings regarding the implementation of more green initiatives at the show. Many participants indicated that there is no room for these initiatives as the show and its content are already overwhelming, especially for first-time attendees. Those participants who were unaware of green initiatives, but who expressed a desire for more initiatives,

indicated that the presences of more such initiatives especially regarding fishing impacts and marine life would be welcome.

3.4.5 Recommendations made by participants

Participants had the following recommendations and suggestions regarding the overall management of Eudi:

- Many participants indicated that many of the major production homes are no longer present at the show, which is a limitation to the show.
- Improved masters' courses should be offered at the show.
- More demonstrations of possible accidents that can occur under water would be beneficial to divers.
- More stalls that offer the latest products, gear, and equipment should be present.
- More interactive opportunities, for example to test latest equipment.
- A greater variety of food stalls.

Table 10: Demographic information on divers interviewed at Eudi 2016

Participant	Gender	Age	Country of origin	Place of origin	Occupation	Number of days at dive show	Number of people in travel party	Average budget to attend dive show (Euro)	Number of years diving	Diving certifications	Preferred places to dive	Reason for attending EUDI	Attendance of other dive shows during 2016	Awareness of green initiatives at EUDI
Participant 1	Male	57	Italy	Torino	Vet and diving instructor	1	2		34	Divemaster with hypoxic trimix certification	Italy	To sell dive books	Boot	Green initiatives in the show seem rare and would be good to have more of them
Participant 2	Female	28	Italy	Cuneo	Nurse	1	2	400	4	Divemaster with deep certification	Italy	Passionate about diving		Green initiatives in the show seem rare and would be good to have more of them
Participant 3	Male	24	Sardinia	Bergamo	Undergraduate student	1	1		13	Diving instructor	Lake Garda and Sardinia	To catch up with friends and curious	Only Eudi	Not enough green initiatives because the event is commercialised, but there should be more green initiatives
Participant 4	Male	41	Sardinia	Asinara	Real estate agent	1	1		22	Diving instructor	Lake Garda and Sardinia	To catch up with friends and curious	Only Eudi	Not enough green initiatives because the event is commercialised, but there should be more green initiatives
Participant 5	Male	28	Italy	Milan		1	4	300		Divemaster and apnoea 60	Sardinia	For work and to meet people	Boot	Unaware of any initiatives.
Participant 6	Female	59	Italy	Milan	Physical education teacher	1	2	100	11	Divemaster and apnoea	Normally in Italy, liking to dive in Maldives and Egypt	Passionate about scuba diving	Only Eudi	Unaware of any, should be more green initiatives at the dive show.
Participant 7	Male	49	Italy	Bologna	Artisan/hydraulic	1	4	500	3	Tech 3 UTR and PADI Deep	Lakes	To catch up with people and understand more about diving. To see equipment and get updates.	Only Eudi	Unaware of any, should be more green initiatives at the dive show.
Participant 8	Male	35	Italy	Bologna	Surveyor	1	4	500	2	Tech 3 UTR and PADI Deep	Lakes	Came to catch up with people and understand more about diving. To see equipment and get updates.	Only Eudi	Unaware of any, should be more green initiatives at the dive show

Participant 9	Male	60	Italy	Ferrara	Storage	1	1		30	Advanced	Islands in Italy and Sardinia	Passionate about diving.	Only Eudi	Limited green initiatives, the rest is equipment and holiday packages, they think that is not that necessary although they think that this event is a bit too technical so if you are a new diver you can get bored. There is not enough about the marine environment.
Participant 10	Male	24	Italy	Ferrara	Insurance	1	1		8	Advanced	Islands in Italy and Sardinia	Passionate about diving.	Only Eudi	Limited green initiatives, the rest is equipment and holiday packages, they think that is not that necessary although they think that this event is a bit too technical so if you are a new diver you can get bored. There is not enough about the marine environment.
Participant 11	Female	36	Italy	Pisa	Undergraduate in marine biology	1	1		10	Instructor	Sicily and Tuscany	Came to meet new people, catch up with other people.		Limited green initiatives at the show.
Participant 12	Female	49	Italy	Monza	High school diploma, student, and waitress	2	6		16	Deep	Sicily and Tuscany	Came to meet new people, catch up with other people.		Limited green initiatives at the show.
Participant 13	Male	44	Italy	Bologna	Salesperson in Graphics	1	1		10	Advanced		Curiosity and for the exhibitors.	Only Eudi	Unaware of any initiatives.
Participant 14	Female	33	Italy	Milan	Swimming teacher	1	4		8	Instructor	Maldives and Liguria	Came to have a look and catch up with people and check out equipment	Only Eudi	Unaware of any initiatives.
Participant 15	Male	35	Italy	Verona	Clerk	1			1	Open water	Lakes	Curiosity and to check new technologies	Only Eudi	Unaware of any initiatives.
Participant 16	Male	45	Italy	Faenza	Surveyor	1	3		16		Italy	To see new things and meet other people.	Only Eudi	Unaware of any initiatives, but it would be interesting.
Participant 17	Male	44	Italy	Faenza	Agriculture	1	3		9		Italy lakes	To see new things and meet other people.	Only Eudi	Unaware of any initiatives, but it would be interesting.
Participant 18	Male	46	Italy	Faenza	Lawyer	1	3		3		Italy and Corsica	To see new things and meet other people.	Only Eudi	Unaware of any initiatives, but it would be interesting.
Participant 19	Male	32	Italy	Ferrara		1	1		16	Instructor	Mediterranean, Sicily, and islands	Curious about Show and to catch up with people.	Only Eudi	Did not see many green initiatives at the event and last year there seemed to be more, there should be more.

Participant 20	Male	47	Italy	Milan		1	2	130	17	Divemaster	Liguria		Only Eudi	More needed
Participant 21	Male	39	Italy	Verona		2		450	17	Trimix normoxic, apnoea instructor, and assistant instructor	Lakes	Passionate about diving.	Boot	Green initiatives needed, especially regarding fishing impacts.
Participant 22	Male	29	Italy			1	1	100	4		Sardinia, Sicilia, Liguria	To see new dive related things and buy wetsuits.	Only Eudi	More green initiatives needed.
Participant 23	Female	22	Italy			1	1	400	6		Sardinia, Sicilia, Liguria	To see new dive related things and buy wetsuits.	Only Eudi	More green initiatives needed.
Participant 24	Male	48	Italy	Torino		1	1	2000	30	Deep	Liguria and red sea	Come to have a look and buy dive related things.	Genova dive show	There are not enough green initiatives because the event is normally for selling diving related equipment and gear.
Participant 25	Female	36	Italy	Torino		1	1		2	Deep	Liguria and red sea	Come to have a look and buy dive related things.	Genova dive show	There are not enough green initiatives because the event is normally for selling diving related equipment and gear.
Participant 26	Female	57	Italy	Bologna		1	1		5	Advanced	Indonesia and Maldives	To see equipment, holidays and to catch up	Only Eudi	Unaware of any green initiatives.
Participant 27	Male	25	Italy	Cuneo		1	4	200	2		Liguria	New stuff, out of curiosity and passion for diving.	Genova dive show	Noticed only Reef Check.
Participant 28	Male	30	Italy	Cuneo		1	4	200	5		Liguria	New stuff, out of curiosity and passion for diving	Genova dive show	Noticed only Reef Check.
Participant 29	Male	50	Italy	Cuneo		1	4	200	16	Instructor	Liguria	New stuff, out of curiosity and passion for diving	Genova dive show	Noticed only Reef Check.
Participant 30	Male	47	Italy	Cuneo		1	4	200	5		Liguria	New stuff, out of curiosity and passion for diving	Genova dive show	Noticed only Reef Check.
Participant 31	Female	42	Italy	Bologna		1	2	300	8	Rescue diver	Rimini, Ravenna, Indonesia, Red Sea	Came for the news and the updates about scuba diving.		Green initiatives seem to be missing and there should be more

3.5 DIVERS ATTENDING EDUCATIONAL/INFORMATIVE PRESENTATIONS AT DUIKVAKER 2017

3.5.1 Introduction and method of research

The second part of Phase 3 focused on the opinion of divers who attended the educational/informative talks and presentations at Duikvaker 2017. This show was chosen, as it is the oldest dive show hosted in The Netherlands. The show had five theatres where the talks were held. Each stage represented speakers on a variety of topics ranging from diving, photography, marine life, diving destinations and equipment. Fieldworkers were allocated a stage and participants were approached once a presentation was over. A total of 12 participants were interviewed. Since the purpose of Green Bubbles is to promote a more sustainable diving industry, the researcher deemed it appropriate to also focus on this aspect at dive shows. Educational/informative presentations and talks can be an ideal way to inform divers and the public on more sustainable scuba diving practices. The objectives were therefore as follow:

- To determine the demographic profile of divers attending educational/informative presentations.
- To determine divers' diving experience.
- To determine divers' opinion regarding educational/informative presentations at dive shows.

In the next section, the findings are discussed.

3.5.2 Demographic profile of participants interviewed

The majority of participants who were interviewed during Duikvaker 2017 were male (67%), while 33% were female (Table 11). On average, participants were 39 years old, originated from The Netherlands (92%) and 8% (only one respondent) were from Australia, spent an average of one day at Duikvaker, previously attended the show for an average of 3.92 times and had a budget of €135 for the show. The main motivational themes identified, i.e. the reasons why participants attended Duikvaker, were for knowledge (38%), followed by curiosity and socialisation (13%, respectively). Thirty-three percent (33%) indicated that they also attended Boot, while 8% (one participant) indicated that they were only attending Duikvaker during 2017 and 8% (one participant) would also attended a local congress.

3.5.3 Participants' diving experience

On average, participants have been diving for nine years with either a dive master or instructor (25% each) or rescue diver (17%) certification. Participants indicated that they mostly dive in The Netherlands (39%), followed by Egypt (19%) and Australia (8%). Other diving destinations mentioned were Cuba, Mexico, Jordan, the Philippines, Spain, and Turkey (4%, respectively).

3.5.4 Opinions regarding educational/informative presentations

Regarding the educational/informative presentations attended by the participants, all participants indicated that they chose the specific presentation due to their interest in either learning something new, getting information on a destination, diving technique, diving activity (e.g. photography) or equipment or simply out of curiosity. Seventy-five percent (75%) of the participants specified that the presentation they attended influenced them in a positive manner. This was mainly due to the expansion of their knowledge on the topic. Other topics participants were also interested in were in marine biology (11%), followed by medical-related issues (8%) and diving destinations (8%). Participants indicated that the knowledge of the speaker/presenter (16%) was the key aspect for a memorable presentation, followed by the quality of the presentation (12%), the ability to convey relevant information (12%) and the topic (8%). The majority of participants (67%) indicated that ideally, presentations should be between 20 and 30 minutes in length. The participants also indicated a need for more environmentally friendly initiatives at Duikvaker as well as more presentations on the topic.

3.5.5 Recommendations made by participants

Regarding the organisation and marketing of Duikvaker, the participants had the following recommendations/suggestions:

- Provide maps and programmes at the entrance to assist visitors with the layout of the dive show.
- Improve signage to assist visitors in finding the different stages and exhibitors.
- A major problem with most of the stages was that the educational/informative presentations that were held had poor audibility due to the music and announcements made in the other areas of the show. This aspect negatively influenced the experience of both the presenters and attendees of the presentations.

Table 10: Demographic profile of participants interviewed at Duikvaker 2017

Participant	Gender	Age	Nationality	Days attending Duikvaker	Years previously attended	Average budget to attend	Motives to attend		Motivational Themes	Number or years diving	Diving certifications	Preferred places to dive	Other dive shows planning to attend during 2017	
Participant 1	Female	46	Netherlands	1	2	10	To attend workshops		Education	2		Netherlands	Local congress	
Participant 2	Male	60	Netherlands	1	15	100	To get information on diving destinations		Knowledge	30	CMAS	Netherlands		
Participant 3	Female	37	Netherlands	1	5	50	To get information on diving and medical issues	To get to know people	Curiosity	Knowledge Socialisation Curiosity	16	Instructor	Netherlands Egypt Turkey	Boot
Participant 4	Female	25	Netherlands	1	6	50	To network		Networking	4	Instructor scuba	Netherlands	Boot	
Participant 5	Male	66	Netherlands	1	1		To get more information		Knowledge	14	Divemaster	Cuba Egypt Netherlands	Only Duikvaker	
Participant 6	Female	41	Netherlands	1	3		To purchase new products		Purchasing	1	Divemaster	Netherlands	Boot	
Participant 7	Female	34	Netherlands	1	3		To be inspired	To gain travelling ideas	Inspiration	10	Divemaster	Netherlands Mexico Philippines	Boot	
Participant 8	Male	42	Netherlands	1	1		To meet new people	See latest trends	Socialisation Knowledge	9	Instructor	Netherlands Spain Egypt		
Participant 9	Female	30	Netherlands	1	4		Exposure to new technology		Exposure	17	Rescue diver	Australia Egypt Jordan		
Participant 10	Female	26	Netherlands	1	1	500	To explore the dive show		Curiosity	1	PADI OW and AOW	Netherlands		
Participant 11	Female	37	Australia	1	4		To attend presentations		Knowledge	5	Rescue diver	Australia Egypt		
Participant 12	Male	26	Netherlands	1	2	100	Member of a dive club	To get information on diving	Knowledge	3	Advanced open water	Netherlands		

Table 12: Opinions regarding educational/informative presentations at Duikvaker 2017

Participant	Presentation topic	Reason for choosing particular presentation	Influence of presentation on behaviour	Other presentation topics interested in attending			Important aspects for a memorable presentation experience				Preferred length for presentations	Need for more environmentally friendly initiatives at Show
Participant 1	De Duikkeuring	Medical interest	N/A	Marine Biology	Medical	Wreck diving	Engaging topic	Knowledge of speaker			30 min	Yes, information on what to do with your garbage.
Participant 2	Duiken adventure trip	Interested in the destination	Yes, confirmed that right choice regarding destination was made	video editing			Engaging topic	Quality of presentation			20-30 min	Yes
Participant 3	Sidemountduiken	Interested in learning	Yes, will perhaps start side diving	Medical	Destination, Bonair		Engaging speaker	Knowledge of speaker			30 min	Yes
Participant 4	Biologie Meerzien	Interested in photography skills	Yes, were looking for aspects more specific to subject.	Vacation destinations	Cave diving		Engaging speaker				10-15 min	Yes
Participant 5	Aquba	Interested in Jordan	No, need more information.				Personal experience and recollections in presentation					Yes, everyone should be more responsible.
Participant 6	Safety	Interested in speakers knowledge	Yes, learned new information	Photography/videos			Well-known speaker	Entertaining presentation	Attractive speaker		10 min	Yes
Participant 7	Kenya	Interested in Kenya as a diving destination	Yes, gained insights into Kenya and it is now a destination to consider	Maldives			Practical information	Information on the best time to travel to destination	Information on attractions and facilities on offer at destination	Information family friendly packages	20 min	Yes, more information needed, and tips on environmentally friendly practices.
Participant 8	Indonesia	Nostalgic reasons	N/A	Marine Biology	Photography		Quality of the presentation	Variety			20-30 min	Yes, there is not enough on the subject.
Participant 9	Freedive fotografie	Interested in underwater photography	Yes, found it interesting the role that it plays in tourism	Scientific presentations			Creating awareness	Getting the central message across			20 min	Yes
Participant 10	GoPro opleidingen: PADI Divemaster courses	Interested inEFR Instructor course	Yes, received the information required				Entertaining	Engaging speaker			20 min	Yes but did not see any at Show.
Participant 11	Freedive fotografie	Fascinated by Freediving	Yes, people need to take action to protect animals	Sea Shepard			Knowledge of presenter	Quality of the presentation			20 min	Yes
Participant 12	Diveplace What the heck is PADI Tech	Interested in Technical diving courses by PADI	Yes, received information on advancing dive skills	Marine biology	Underwater photography		Knowledge of presenter	Clear overview of what to expect	Opportunity to ask questions		15 min	

4. IMPLICATIONS REGARDING DIVE SHOWS

Based on the findings presented in this report, the following recommendations are made regarding the sustainable management of dive shows.

4.1 Implications for the case study dive destinations

Based on the interviews with the operators in the case study destinations of Portofino and Ponta do Ouro, the following implications are discussed.

4.1.1 Portofino

- The participants interviewed expressed concerns and the need for greater collaboration between the operators in Portofino and the MPA. The participants recommended that it is vital that the operators and the MPA work together to devise a strategy on the best way to promote Portofino as a dive destination. Currently, the respective dive operations promote their business at dive shows independently. However, since attending and exhibiting at dive shows are expensive, such a strategy will be more cost-effective and will allow greater promotion of Portofino.
- If the afore-mentioned strategy is not possible, dive operators should realise that attending dive shows is a long-term investment and can provide valuable visibility of the operation to existing and potential new clients. Dive shows are also the perfect platform to stay abreast of the latest diving trends, equipment as well as the changing needs of the market. However, attendance should be carefully planned and the envisaged outcome(s) that the operator wants to achieve for the business should form the basis for attending. Attendance of dive shows, both locally and internationally, could be a valuable strategy to ensure the long-term sustainability of the business.
- The participants also expressed the need for more affordable localised dive shows or fairs in the area. This is another aspect that would require greater collaboration with not only the MPA, but also among the operators in Portofino.

4.1.2 Ponta do Ouro

- Compared to the interviews conducted in Portofino, the dive operators in Ponta do Ouro expressed very different opinions regarding the attendance of dive shows. However, these differences could be ascribed to the fact that there are not many dive shows held in South Africa (neighbouring country) for these operators to attend. Currently, there is only one major dive show, which is combined with outdoor lifestyle and boating. Therefore, these operators mainly rely on word-of-mouth promotion of their business or internal marketing initiatives. The participants also did not express the need for more than one dive show annually as attendance is expensive and return-on-investment is low. However, they did indicate a need for local conferences and smaller events held in the area of

Ponta do Ouro. These smaller, more localised events could be an ideal opportunity to promote Ponta do Ouro as a dive destination and increase the number of divers travelling to the area.

4.2 Implications for exhibitors in general

- For exhibitors, including dive operators, attendance is a long-term financial investment, and patience is therefore key. Exhibitors should realise that one may not see return-on-investments from only attending and exhibiting at a dive show once. Therefore, attendance should be a long-term strategy to promote the business.
- The participants interviewed indicated that when exhibiting at dive shows, a goal-oriented strategy should be followed. As mentioned under section 6.1, the exhibitor should keep the envisaged outcome(s) from attending, in mind. For example, if the purpose is to network, there is not necessarily a need to for a stand. On the other hand, if visibility and building a client base are the aims, a stand is required and greater attention should be given to the stand and how it is presented. Stands should create be inviting and captivating and visitors should be informed of the different operations in an engaging manner. Therefore, it is key to appoint the right person(s) to attend the dive show to promote the business.
- Since personal interaction with clients is vital, dive shows are the ideal platform to achieve this. Interactions should be memorable and could be an inexpensive way to promote the business.
- From the interviews, it is evident that the needs of the market who attends dive shows are changing. Therefore, it is important for exhibitors to consider these changing needs and adapt their exhibitions and especially their marketing approaches accordingly.
- It is paramount that destinations and dive operators work together especially when wanting to exhibit at dive shows as this will allow sharing the cost of the stand(s). In addition, when marketing and attending dive shows internationally, it would perhaps be more effective to sell diving holiday packages to destinations and not diving alone. Therefore, a more holistic approach should be followed when exhibiting at dive shows as this will be detrimental for the long-term viability of dive show attendance.

4.3 Implications for dive shows in general

- **General management**
 - The dive operators, exhibitors, and visitors interviewed expressed the need for more affordable and accessible dive shows. Organisers of these dive shows could consider introducing group package discounts, especially to visitors. This strategy could encourage visitors to travel in larger groups and to stay longer in the host area increasing the economic spin-offs from dive shows. This could also encourage visitors to travel further to attend the show and thereby increase the number of international visitors compared to local visitors. Special packages with reduced rates could also be considered for exhibitors, especially to

those who have been exhibiting at a particular show for years. This could be a way to increase loyalty among exhibitors and long-term exhibiting at the shows.

- As indicated by the dive operators in Portofino, combining dive shows with other outdoor products and activities in South Africa works; however, each component in the show should be equally promoted and clearly distinguished as the diving component in these shows is currently neglected. Apart from the fact that only one major dive show is held in South Africa that dive operators in Ponta do Ouro can attend, the communication between the organisers and exhibitors should be improved. Information regarding dates and costs should be readily updated online or on social media pages to assist dive operators to plan their attendance in advance. Marketing efforts should be expanded to countries bordering South Africa. The participants also mentioned that there is currently no fixed date(s) for the Getaway Show in South Africa, which makes planning to attend difficult. They suggested that the show be held during dive month in South Africa.
- The exhibitors included in the research stated that greater communication and collaboration between dive show organisers and exhibitors is needed. Information should be readily available on the process of exhibiting, the associated costs, and the requirements for exhibiting in terms of stand size etc.

- **Marketing**

- Dive shows should intensively market the experience to visitors. The participants interviewed indicated that the main reasons for attending dive shows were to socialise, because they are passionate about diving and to be exposed to the latest dive trends and equipment. Promotional campaigns should therefore emphasise that attending the dive show is the ideal way to relax, socialise and meet new people, while at the same time being exposed to the latest diving trends in an educational and informative but entertaining way.
- Coupled to the motives above, visitors indicated that the latest trends and products should be key features at dive shows. Therefore, it is important for the organisers to consider this when selecting exhibitors and to intensively market these aspects at the show.
- From an accessibility and practical point of view, it is important not to overwhelm visitors with displays. The different stages and exhibitor stands should therefore allow enough space to improve personal interaction between exhibitors and visitors.
- Visitors expressed the need for more interactive displays regarding the use of the latest equipment as well as safety demonstrations.

- **Environmental and educational displays and talks**

- Regarding more environmentally and educational displays at dive shows, the visitors, operators and exhibitors interviewed conveyed mixed feelings. The majority of participants indicated the importance of such campaigns; however, they feel that dive shows may not be the ideal place to convey such messages, since visitors are already overwhelmed by the

various product offerings. However, it is recommended that this aspect be incorporated into dive shows in subtle ways, for example posters, and should be an aspect that exhibitors should be encouraged to include in their displays.

- The informative and educational talks could be the ideal platform to include more environmentally conscious campaigns. Since these talks are usually divided into different themes, dive shows should consider including sessions where this aspect is the main theme. The visitors who attend these talks stated that the main reason to attend these sessions is that they are interested in learning something new. Informing visitors about this important aspect could therefore encourage them to be more aware of the marine environment and their own diving practices.
- The topics participants were interested in were marine biology, followed by medical-related issues and topics on diving destinations. Environmentally friendly campaigns could easily be incorporated in all of these topics.
- Since early exposure is essential, it is recommended that there are sessions aimed at the youth to educate children and school groups on the importance of protecting the marine environment. This could also be an effective way to get the youth involved in diving.
- When selecting speakers, visitors indicated that the knowledge of the speaker on a particular topic is vital for a memorable experience. Therefore, organisers of dive shows should carefully select speakers based on their knowledge and experience on the topic. Speakers should also be encouraged to have interactive and engaging presentations, as this was another aspect participants indicated as important. Ideally, presentations should be 20 minutes with five to 10 minutes allocated for possible questions as the interviewed participants did not indicate the need for longer presentations.
- Topics on specifically dive destinations were also popular among the participants. This can be another ideal way for the case studies to market their operations in the destinations. If greater collaboration between the operators and the respective MPAs can be achieved, the educational talks could be an opportunity to promote the destinations as a whole with specific emphasis on the diving opportunities.